

ORIGINAL ARTICLE OPEN ACCESS

Reading Through Traces: Xaverian Strategies of Including Chinese Folk Deities' Statues in Museum Displays and Fictions in Parma, Italy

Valentina Gamberi (she/her)

Department of Asian Studies, Palacký University Olomouc, Olomouc, Czech Republic

Correspondence: Valentina Gamberi (valentina.gamberi@upol.cz)

Received: 24 May 2025 | **Revised:** 10 September 2025 | **Accepted:** 14 January 2026

Keywords: Chinese folk deities' statues | missionary collecting | missionary museum | missionary writing | trace

ABSTRACT

This work reflects on the presence of a desacralized Buddha statue in the Museum of Chinese Art and Ethnography, established in Parma, Italy, in 1901 by Xaverian missionaries. The Buddha's hollowed back is a potent trace of the transnational interactions between these Roman Catholic missionaries and folk believers from the Henan region (mainland China) in the early 20th century. As a trace, it is a multitemporal artifact accounting for missionary and local ambivalence toward statues of folk deities. Whilst missionaries saw the latter as a tool for their preaching practice and the target of iconoclasm, local folk believers—regardless of their religious affiliation—feared the residual spiritual potency of folk deities' statues discarded after religious conversions and iconoclasm. Traces of both approaches toward folk deities' statues emerge from missionary literary accounts and are partly retraceable in curatorial practice. Analyzing traces in missionary fiction suggests direction in provenance research blocked by inaccessible and fragmented archives.

1 | Preamble: A Hollowed Buddha Statue

One July morning in Parma, Italy, I was lost in thought when I encountered a small wooden Buddha statue stored in the Museum of Chinese Art and Ethnography. The statue was not different from others I had observed in Taiwanese public and private temples since 2019: carved in wood, it was painted afterward with what seemed to be lacquer. However, it presented a hollow in the upper level of its back. The presence of the hollow triggered two contradictory feelings: of the familiar and the uncanny, resonating with my ethnographic fieldwork among Daoist priests in Taiwan in 2024. In folk religion professed by Han and Hakka ethnicities across Asia—a syncretism between Daoism, Buddhism, and Confucianism—sacred matter is placed in a hollow carved out from the statues' back and sealed with a wooden stopper during the *rushen* (入神) ritual, one of a series of ritual steps that enable a piece of wood to become the incarnation of a god.¹ *Rushen*, more precisely, is the process through

which the karmic bond between the worshipper and the god's spirit is established (Reich 2024), defining a series of ritual obligations that can only be fulfilled by retrieval of the god's spirit in heaven, which is commonly referred to as *tuishen* (退神). After *tuishen*, the sacred items must be removed from the statue so it can be kept as an art specimen or stored. In so doing, the statue's hollow—which was sealed during *rushen*—is unsealed and becomes visible again on the statue's back. This process prevents any spirit from taking possession of the statue, thereby polluting anyone who continues to interact with it. What I could see in Parma—the hollowed back—was, therefore, a trace of *tuishen*, see Figure 1.

The hollowed Buddha acquires further meaning if we consider that the Museum of Chinese Art and Ethnography is a missionary museum, inaugurated in 1901 as part of the Xaverian Missionary Institute run by Guido Maria Conforti (1865–1931), now a Roman Catholic saint. Missionary museums, flourishing in the

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2026 The Author(s). *Museum Anthropology* published by Wiley Periodicals LLC on behalf of American Anthropological Association.

FIGURE 1 | The hollowed Buddha (inventory number cn0680), 2022. Photograph by Valentina Gamberi, reproduced with the permission of the Museo d'Arte Cinese ed Etnografico.

19th and 20th centuries across Protestant (Hasinoff 2010, 2011; Wingfield 2017) and Catholic (Amaral 2020; Brevaglieri 2022; Corbey and Weener 2015; Kreps 2024; Scholz 2025) churches, reflected the broader approaches of each missionary congregation toward materiality. These museums were sites of memorialization of the congregations and their founders, representations of cultural and religious alterities, and displays of “trophy” (Loder-Neuhold 2019) of successful conversions. Missionary museums supported, along with printed media (Jensz and Acke 2013), the theological and “civilizing” importance of religious conversions. The name of the Xaverian congregation’s journal, *Fede e Civiltà* (Faith and Civilization), recalled the missionaries’ purpose. In the case of Catholic missionary congregations, museums acquired further meaning with the Second Vatican Council and the Encyclic *Maximum illud* (1919), according to which non-European cultures could reveal Christian truth. Religious conversions “purified” non-European cultures from idolatry, whilst retaining their specificities. By displaying or describing artifacts from “idolatric civilizations,” missionaries aimed at convincing the museumgoers of the cultural richness of China, whilst at-testing missionary success in suppressing the “idolatry” of folk believers in the Henan region. Missionary media also instructed prospective missionaries about what they should accomplish “in the field,” namely, deeply understanding non-European cultures whilst, through intercultural skills, eradicating idolatric cults. Missionary collecting and writing thus served, legitimized, and reinforced each congregation’s “missionary strategy”.

What can the hollowed Buddha I encountered in Parma reveal about Xaverian “missionary strategy” and the relationships between missionaries and local folk believers in the Henan region? If that god statue was part of religious conversions, when its hollow was unsealed (before or after its collection), who unsealed it,

and why become crucial questions. It could have been unsealed as part of an iconoclastic attack or after *tuishen*, thereby respecting local knowledge about Chinese god statues.

This work guides readers through my journey to understanding the presence of the Buddha statue in the museum. By following it as a trace leading back to the missionary presence in Henan province, I elicit broader missionary approaches and ambivalences toward Chinese folk deities’ statues, as well as speculate on folk believers’ responses to missionary preaching. As will be seen in this study, Chinese folk deities’ statues disgusted and, at the same time, attracted Xaverian missionaries (Wu 2016). New converts, who were still transitioning from their habitual and embodied ritual practice to their new faith (Kao 2020), felt menaced by their statues’ “sacred residue” (Beekers 2016) once they ceased to worship them.

Framing the hollowed statue as a trace, this study reconceptualizes traces as methodological tools for assessing missionary collections. Despite limited accessibility to museum archives in Parma, I could infer folk believers in Henan and missionaries’ approaches toward folk deities’ statues *under the grain* (Stoler 2013) from missionary literature and recreate them as experiential reveries while I read them on the basis of my ethnographic fieldwork.² Traces are therefore material and immaterial presences of the past and how we engage with them, whether explicitly—through our senses—or implicitly—by reconstructing the past atmosphere as it unfolds in the pages of missionary literature. Traces go beyond standard “historical sources” and, for this reason, can be useful for studying museum collections in which information is insufficient for thorough provenance research.

This work articulates this new definition of traces by showing its methodological applicability. It further describes Xaverian’s “missionary strategy” and the role played by the museum collection as reverberating through the traces accessed during research. It then illustrates how two missionaries, Cipriano Silvestri (1872–1955) and Eugenio Pelerzi (1881–1942), described complementary approaches that were part of the broader Xaverian missionary strategy. On the one hand, Silvestri studied Chinese folk religion by excavating Chinese folk god statues’ interiors, thereby enacting a scientific understanding of Chinese folk religion that was nonetheless borderline iconoclasm. On the other hand, Pelerzi envisaged Chinese material culture as a facilitator of conversions and missionaries’ cultural adaptation whilst instrumentalizing new converts’ anxieties toward Chinese folk deities’ statues in his novels. The study finally returns to the statue, trying to formulate a hypothesis of what could have happened to it based on the preceding analysis of missionary traces.

2 | Inaccessible Museum Archives: Toward a Review of Traces

“Trace” is a highly charged concept in the social sciences, particularly history and anthropology. In anthropological research, traces are multi-stratified, multi-historical material artifacts (Napolitano 2015; Smith 2018). They reveal how we relate to the past and how it intrudes into our lives. This experience of

the past reverberating through the trace as its material medium is twofold. As in the case of the hollowed Buddha, traces can induce “revelation, mantic technique, oneiric, prophetic, or otherwise ‘inspired’” (Palmié and Stewart 2016, 213) forms of knowledge. Traces can even generate disruptive epiphanies or hauntings that we can barely link to a codified system of symbols and meanings (Corin 2020). How we relate to traces, though, is also selective: we engage with portions of the past that affectively charged aspects of our present existence (Palmié and Stewart 2019). Consequently, we can relate to the past for legitimizing our status quo or for subverting it. For instance, traces are remnants of the colonial past that still reverberate with neo-colonial dynamics in the present, such as establishing allegedly universal heritage values that reproduce Eurocentric beliefs and representations (Bodenstein et al. 2024; Meyer 2024).

In historical research, Carlo Ginzburg (2013 [1986]) suggests how small particulars, linked to data found in heterogeneous sources and places, might reveal aspects and dynamics that would remain obscure through a literal analysis of archival material. Provenance research derives from Ginzburg's suggestion (Mooren et al. 2022; Verband der Museen der Schweiz 2022). It follows the traces or trajectories that museum artifacts and their collectors left in the various contexts of usage and exchange before they arrived at the museum. The complex network between artifacts' producers, owners, collectors, and museum curators assumes further significance once artifacts enter museum collections: we can trace their different representations and usages by looking at the stratification of exhibition and collections' catalog, conservation reports, and museum entries compiled in different periods and according to different cataloguing criteria. Marsh calls this retracing artifacts' provenance an “ethnography of the trace” (Marsh 2016). As readers may notice, in provenance research, traces might be considered both material elements—inscriptions, signs of deterioration, documents—but also processes in which different locations, usages, and concepts are linked or *traced* across different temporalities.

This work partly suggests broadening these conceptualizations of traces. As in other colonial-era museum collections, I had to deal with a substantial lack of archival material that could enable thorough provenance research. I was not permitted to visit the missionary museum archives and storage rooms on my own. In addition, the museum archivist provided catalog entries for the artifacts I wanted to examine, but these lacked associated archival material—such as purchase receipts or missionaries' diaries. I soon realized that the Museum of Chinese Art and Ethnography's collections had not been systematically organized or thoroughly archived.

In response to this lack of archival material that connected directly to these objects, this paper analyses alternative traces to those that we could usually find in museums to infer possible usages of museum collections. By “alternative traces,” I refer to immaterial conditions or elements, such as ideas, atmospheres, embodied feelings, and practices that emerge from written words, reverberate in material traces such as the hollowed Buddha, and resonate with contemporary practices, such as *tuishen* and museum curatorship. Beyond finding and connecting clues for reconstructing a past event, we can implicitly infer an event or an approach from the style used for compiling

a museum entry or shaping a story. In particular, this study utilizes traces found in the missionary congregation's library and archive. Although established for different purposes than the museum storage rooms and archives, the Xaverian library and archive can provide us with traces of the missionaries' encounters with folk believers and their deities' statues in Henan. This vast literary corpus shows how materiality played a crucial role in sharpening the “missionary strategy” of which the Museum of Chinese Art and Ethnography was part.

In this work, I use heterogeneous writings realized for the congregation's newspaper *Fede e civiltà*, missionary novels, and theatrical pieces as traces. In particular, I focus on the novels by Eugenio Pelerzi, one of the most prolific missionary novelists of the Xaverian congregation, and an ethnographic account written by Father Silvestri for *Faith and Civilization*—as directly related to the practice of carving hollows into Chinese folk deities' statues—and compare them with other sources found in the newspaper. In these sources, we do not have objective, historical “facts,” but partial ideas of past events that still reverberate in our experience of traces in the present.

The lack of an “objective” reconstruction of missionary practices derives from these writings' ambiguous boundaries with reality. As a recurrent style in missionary writings, real testimonies witnessed by missionaries are mixed with imagination. Missionaries initially intertwined real experience and phantasies in the short articles released for *Fede e Civiltà*, then expanding the stories' plots in larger formats, either novels or theatrical pieces. Whilst articles were presented as “reports” from the mission, novels and other fictional writings did not explicitly refer to missionaries' experiences. Missionaries' narrative goals also filtered and distorted folk believers' voices and perspectives, transforming them into *exempla* of good converts and martyrs, but totally malleable by and subaltern to missionaries.

For instance, in a series of articles for *Fede e Civiltà* (Pelerzi 1919), Pelerzi reported his historical research on the figure of Giuseppe Siao, one of the first converts persecuted in the Henan region, interviewing Giuseppe's family members and documenting the places of his martyrdom. The reports were apologetic texts dedicated to Giuseppe's persecution rather than rigorous reconstructions of the events and an accurate portrait of Giuseppe as a complex, agentic character according to historiographical methods. Pelerzi subsequently published a novel on Giuseppe's story (Pelerzi 1921) that largely rearranged and reproduced the articles in *Fede e Civiltà*.

Even though the writing style created a discrepancy between missionary accounts and what happened *in the field*—as confirmed by secondary sources (Harrison 2013) and informal discussions with contemporary missionaries—it is still relevant to this study. What we find are, therefore, fantasies, ideal projections, and imaginary reconstructions about the congregation's missionary strategy and its relationship with folk believers. Each missionary personally elaborated on what a missionary strategy meant for his subjective experience *in the field*.

Missionary narratives are, therefore, historical traces that are *intrinsically anachronistic* and biased: they ideologically sustained missionary collecting plans rather than describing

historical facts. Methodologically, I tried to capture nuances and speculate on counter-voices to missionary accounts. As in my first epiphanic encounter with the hollowed Buddha, I reflected on certain descriptions of converts based on my fieldwork which expanded my knowledge of *tuishen*. I also asked selected interlocutors among ritual specialists and temple committee members to comment on the accuracy of Silvestri's article. Second, through formal and informal interviews of museum staff and missionaries in Parma and Taiwan, as well as observations on the museum's permanent exhibition, I understood how historical traces are reworked in present museum and missionary practices.³ What unfolds in the following is a detailed description of some hypotheses on the presence of the hollowed Buddha in the museum.

3 | The Museum of Chinese Art and Ethnography: Materiality as “Missionary Strategy”

When the Xaverian Congregation's Regulations were drafted in 1898, Conforti urged missionaries to collect art and ethnographic artifacts from China to educate missionaries about Chinese culture and attract Italian lay supporters of the mission and the institute. This collecting enterprise was interrupted by the expulsion of all the religious congregations from China at the end of the civil war. The museum, nonetheless, still acquired artifacts from other areas, including Taiwan, when new missions were established.

Father Giovanni Bonardi (1881–1974), who returned to Italy from China in 1911 to assist Guido Maria Conforti in managing the institute, became the director of both the institute and the museum. According to one missionary responsible for the archives, Bonardi began to hone a “technique” for training younger seminarists and missionaries in Chinese culture.

To understand Bonardi's technique, we must begin with his essay *Nel campo delle missioni* (In the Mission Field 1921). He conceptualized collecting and cultural research as parts of what he defined as missionary “strategy” (Bonardi 1921, 17). According to Bonardi, as lay soldiers followed military strategies, missionaries similarly focused on winning over a spiritual enemy. In addition, in Bonardi's view, missionaries had cultural sensitivity and mediating skills that soldiers and colonial authorities often lacked. Chinese and Catholic material culture significantly mediated the metamorphosis of converts and the missionary review of Chinese culture. This strategy started as Bonardi's field experience and then circulated and was transmitted as the “strategy” of the whole Xaverian congregation.

Bonardi's “strategy” was implemented upon his return from China and reflected a broader process, in the Catholic church, of incorporating ethnographic methods in missionary practice. In 1911, he arrived at the Parmesan Mother House with a rich collection of boxes with Chinese artifacts that expanded the existing Xaverian collection. In 1913, as rector of the institute and together with Father Popoli, he participated in the Ethnological Week in Leuven organized by Father Wilhem Schmidt (1868–1954), one of the chief advocates of adopting ethnographic methods and anthropological knowledge among missionaries and the organizer of the Universal Vatican Exposition in 1925. The two

Xaverians' experience of the Ethnological Week was reported in *Fede e civiltà* and Father Popoli's diaries (Ferro 2014, 87–90). Participants also visited the missionary museum in Terveuren, of which Father Schmidt was the director. In the same year, Father Bonardi established a cycle of conferences on Chinese culture and began to manage the editorial board of the newspaper *Fede e Civiltà*. Although Bonardi was influenced by Schmidt in developing a form of missionary collecting across different congregations that standardized the relationships between the Vatican and its several regional provinces (Amaral 2020), he also came to design a “missionary strategy” independently and based on his experience in China.

Bonardi, by managing the institute, the museum, and the newspaper, linked missionary methodologies of conversions to public outreach in Italian public opinion, both legitimizing the missionary anthropological and intellectual role in encountering Chinese culture and attracting prospective missionaries among Italian youngsters. Bonardi's endeavors were materially mediated and acted as *emotional devices*, motivating prospective missionaries and converts to start their spiritual path. Chinese and Catholic religious artifacts were assembled, redistributed, exchanged, and reproduced across the Mother House and the Chinese mission. The missionary museum, therefore, enabled different forms of display and narrative.

By “assembling,” I mean that both Catholic and Chinese ritual artifacts were conjured up to create a sense of sympathy and identification with the missionaries. As a missionary explained during my visits to the Institute's archives, Bonardi gathered and systematized relics and belongings of the congregation's founder and martyrs in China; these items are now stored in a special collection of the congregation's Institute, see Figure 2. Creating a space dedicated to such matters was also part of other European missionary congregations' displays, including the Vatican Exposition (Può-Mate 1913, 1; Loder-Neuhold 2019; Gasparotto 2018, 227–235). Material artifacts and relics were intertwined with capillary propaganda on missionaries as role models for Italian youngsters and were distributed across various media, ranging from *Fede e*

FIGURE 2 | The exhibitive space dedicated to the first missionaries and martyrs at the Xaverian Institute, 2024. Photograph by Valentina Gamberi, reproduced with the permission of the Museo d'Arte Cinese ed Etnografico.

Civiltà and missionary novels to the missionary cinema, initiated in 1924 with the movie *Il nido degli aquilotti* (The Little Eagles' Nest), an expression used by Conforti to indicate his Institute's seminarists and missionaries.

“Exotic” artifacts and relics, reproduced in the press or on movie screens and displayed in the Mother House, temporary fairs, exhibitions, and markets, consolidated romantic fantasies of the missionary as a spiritual soldier. As narrated by the museum staff, the practice of selling such artifacts from all over the world is so ingrained in the collective memory of Parmesans' elderly generations that even today some random visitors ask where the market is located.

As stated by Iurman (2016, 9), *Fede e Civiltà* redistributed its museum collections as illustrations of its articles, as well as in postcards sent as souvenirs for journal subscriptions and donations. As forms of engagement with the readership, some financial contributors to the newspaper also received museum artifacts as prizes, or were allowed to name newly converted Chinese children after readers' beloved ones. Museum collections were also distributed in missionary theatrical scripts, novels, and movies, described and recreated as the plot's scenography. Missionaries even moved their collections to use them in on-stage performances. One of the missionaries I talked to during my archival research confirmed that this high mobility of museum artifacts has occurred until recent decades. For instance, he knew that part of the museum collection was lent to other Parmesan parishes for children's plays.

The distribution and circulation of artifacts at various levels, from the market to photographic reproduction, also reveal the symbiotic relationship that missionaries had with their collections. The items were initially on view in the seminar rooms, rather than being a more structured exhibit as in later displays, so that missionaries and their students could freely sense, look at, experience, and teach Chinese folk religion. This direct engagement with collections created a sense of subjectivity and a personal bond between missionary collectors and their collections. It is therefore understandable why Xavierian collections were fragmented, manipulated, and moved from one location to another, as they followed different criteria than museum preservation and conservation.

Some Catholic material artifacts were extremely porous and recursive, including being shipped back and forth between Italy and China. Religious artifacts thus acquired a double life as part of the Italian seminary and the Chinese mission to serve as tools for motivating missionaries and attracting prospective converts. For instance, a painting of the Madonna della Strada (worshipped by Saint Xavier and Ignatius), realized by Ulisse Passani (1848–1933) and donated to Conforti, was shipped to China to provide spiritual comfort to the missionaries (Ferro 2019, 24). Its arrival at the mission is attested by a letter to Luigi Calza (1906–1944), the archbishop of Honanfu, dated the 28th of November 1924. The painting is now on the altar of the main sanctuary in the institute back in Italy. The high mobility of Catholic artifacts, mobilized between China and Italy, created a terrain of material exchanges between the missionaries and prospective converts, orienting the latter's sensitivity toward Catholic worship. Readers must bear in mind this creative,

whilst ambivalent, usage of Catholic and Chinese statuary when examining Silvestri and Pelerzi's writings.

4 | Silvestri's Excavations of Chinese Folk Deities' Statues: Missionary Ambivalence

Missionaries manipulated Chinese folk deities' statues as part of scrutinizing a scientific specimen. An example is the practice of excavating their interiors, as attested in an article by Cipriano Silvestri printed in *Fede e Civiltà* (Silvestri 1915a). This practice is also attested in the museum catalog, which Father Giuseppe Toscano (1911–2003), former museum director, realized in the 1960s. Toscano (1965, 193–194) refers to a bronze statue of Manjusri in which consecration material was found. This material is currently in the museum's permanent display, which does not mention the provenance of Manjusri's statue and simply describes it as small ritual implements. These attestations might explain why sacred material in the interior of some statues was collected and has subsequently been cataloged without mentioning its provenance from a religious statue.

In contrast to other missionaries before Silvestri, who simply explained the presence of holes in Chinese folk deities' statues as a matter of pragmatics (ensuring easier transport of the statues or as a lack of technical dexterity) or a sign of the Apocalypse,⁴ Father Silvestri believed that hollows must be meaningful in Chinese folk religion. He initially excavated the interior of the statues, finding either inscriptions and invocations on paper or insects and snakes. The article and the pictures showing hollowed gods or gods with sealed backs do not indicate whether he collected the statues himself after conversions, purchased them in secondhand shops or temples, or excavated them during his visits to temples. He subsequently described a consecration ritual that occurred while he was in what seems to be the Daoist temple complex in the Wudang Mountains (武當山), associated with the Lord of North, Xuantian Shangdi. The report does not identify this location unambiguously since the transliteration (*U tan*) does not correspond to the current *pinyin*.

While sleeping in the “pagoda,” a series of gunshots woke him up. His servants said that the gunshots were caused by the “bonzi di Laotze” (Laotze's bonzes; Daoist priests) during their devotions. The following morning, Silvestri asked the wood-carver of the “pagoda” what had happened. He narrated that he was about to complete the statue of the god of thunder (雷神, Leishen), introducing five different insects into its hole. After he made an incantation, the spirit of a snake manifested itself by whistling. He consequently “imprisoned” the spirit and triggered gunshots for Leishen, signaling that the god can intervene in human life. Father Silvestri subsequently reported a similar ritual with a Leishen statue he had witnessed in the Hubei mountains. In these accounts of how Silvestri understood the function of holes in Chinese folk deities' statues, he probably described *rushen* ceremonies, as further confirmed by fieldwork with selected participants in Taiwan.

What could be understood from this piece is not the ethnographic accuracy of the missionaries' descriptions but rather a mixture of fear, curiosity, and disgust that was eventually used, in the missionary rhetoric, to justify their presence in China.

For instance, Pelerzi described his feelings in this respect (1920, 147): “When I destroy these old images that stole the worship of the real God for several years, although I hate them from the bottom of my heart, I feel disgusted and try not to be seen by the pagans for not alimending hatred and resentment” (Pelerzi 1920, 147; my translation). In the case of Silvestri, he was unsure whether his excavations could bother the insects and their spirits (“stuzzicarli”), but, at the same time, considered himself free to do whatever he wanted with the “idols,” from photographing them to smashing them on the floor.

Silvestri’s ambivalence is in line with other articles in *Fede e Civiltà*, which often emphasized the moral and material decay of Henan temples and their clergy, usually visited by the local worshippers only for personal gains and open to secular and mundane activities such as smoking, playing card games, or housing the public market (Pelerzi 1922c, 1924b, 19, 24; Silvestri 1915b). Missionaries sarcastically described Chinese folk deities as grinning monsters composed of different animal parts pieced together without apparent logic (Bonardi 1904, 122; Pelerzi 1922b, 134; Silvestri 1915b, 169), on the model of the medieval and Renaissance *Homo monstrum* (Mitter 1992). At the same time, however, Chinese folk deities were not perceived as really menacing; missionaries mockingly described how folk believers themselves freely disposed of them if dissatisfied with their protection, insulting them, throwing them in the mud, or even mutilating them (Pelerzi 1922b, 134–135; 1922c, 92–94). For this reason, missionaries felt they could dispose of these Chinese folk deities’ statues as they liked, even taking out their sacred interiors.

Taking Chinese folk deities’ statues as study objects, fragmenting them, and deconsecrating them were part and parcel of missionary ambivalence toward Chinese folk religion. Such rituals and beliefs must be studied and collected, identifying which ritual and theological aspects could be ethically comparable to Catholicism and incentivized as such in the process of conversion whilst condemning as depravity what could only seem superstition.

5 | Becoming the Other: Pelerzi’s *Incinesarsi*

Father Eugenio Pelerzi’s engagement with Chinese material culture must be contextualized within his personal review of the broader Xaverian “missionary strategy.” He defined the importance of understanding and embodying Chinese culture: if, in the beginning, Chinese artifacts, daily habits, and behaviors appeared either too simple or too subtle for a European sensitivity, a gradual absorption and mimesis of Chinese culture could allow the missionary (and Italian readers) to appreciate its beauty and richness. It is through this cultural internship that the missionary can, subsequently, communicate with folk believers so that his preaching can reflect Chinese sensitivities. He described this process as “becoming Chinese” (or *incinesarsi*; Pelerzi 1924a, 55).

Pelerzi talked through the language of Chinese folk religion but transformed orientations toward its ritual implements, such as god statues, and subtly introduced Catholic materiality. In particular, Pelerzi focused on the cult of the Virgin Mary and the

erection of a church in 1921, dedicated to the Virgin of Grace. The latter was based on a sacred icon reproduced on the model of the homonymous church in Pelerzi’s hometown, Berceto, in the Parmesan Apennines, which was donated to Pelerzi during a visit of Luigi Calza to Parma for his consecration as archbishop of Honanfu. Pelerzi was active in establishing a pilgrimage related to the icon and fostering the production of religious icons, crosses, and rosaries that could be used by his parish’s prospective and new converts. Italian benefactors also donated ritual implements as advertised in the bulletin of *Fede e civiltà*.

The Virgin Mary’s materiality and ritual practices played a fundamental role in Pelerzi’s novel *La figlia del mandarino* (The Mandarin’s Daughter, 1922), in which the protagonist’s attitudes toward Chinese folk religion and Catholicism were reoriented and transformed. The novel focuses on the encounter of two girls, Lucia, the daughter of a Christian family, and Siang, the Mandarin’s daughter, who shared the dormitory in a “pagan” female school they attended. Siang was nosy about Lucia’s eccentricities, such as her Italian baptismal name and Catholic daily worship. Siang’s curiosity culminated when Lucia, in contrast with the rest of the school, wanted to go alone to the institute’s storage closet, where a Buddha statue, a residual trace of an old, deconsecrated pagoda, was placed, usually scaring students. It was believed that during the night the Buddha could become a man, menacing human beings around him. Consequently, anyone who needed to use the storage closet should be accompanied to protect them from the Buddha’s attacks (Pelerzi 1922a, 14–16).

The narrator’s statements about students’ fear of their school’s Buddha resounds with occasional talks I heard in Taiwan around Chinese folk deities’ statues that, for a vast array of reasons, might be abandoned or left in a house or around temples. A ritually unattended statue is often perceived as dangerous. The divine spirit that imbued the statue since its consecration might vindicate worshippers’ negligence by attacking them, or it might abandon the statue and return to heaven. The statue thus becomes a vessel for other spirits or ghosts, polluting those who come into contact with it. It is therefore particularly significant how Pelerzi subtly introduced a context of general ritual disuse and folk believers’ approaches toward ritually unattended sacred matter, as in other missionary accounts related to the decay of Chinese folk deities’ statues, as we will see below. This is implicit in the plot’s narrative as a trace of Pelerzi’s ethnographic understanding of folk believers’ fears toward discarded sacred matter and its adaptation to the Catholic cause.

The story continues with Lucia declaring she was not afraid of what she considered a mere block of wood, echoing the missionary writing’s standpoint. Once Siang could ascertain Lucia’s indifference toward the closet’s Buddha, she explicitly declared her eagerness to know why Lucia lived in a different world from the rest of the campus (Pelerzi 1922a, 24–27).

It was Siang’s participation in the Catholic mass in the parish of Lucia’s family that further transformed Siang’s attitude toward religious iconography and statuary, to the point of conversion to Catholicism and even entering a monastic life. This mass took place in the church dedicated to Maria delle Grazie in Honan, the parish established by Pelerzi. The church is described in the novel as revolving around the sacred aura of the Virgin Mary’s

statue, whose “kind gaze” attracts visitors’ attention. Pelerzi’s narrative emphasizes the importance of the material assemblage constituted by the church architecture, the Virgin Mary’s statue, and the presence of clergy in orienting and guiding visitors’ spiritual reactions, such as that of Siang. The fact that the account of the spiritual awakening of Siang is accompanied by the “missionary’s testimony” adds a sense of veracity and confirms that what happened to Siang was the usual mechanism of spiritual transformation and conversion observed among other Chinese visitors to the church (Pelerzi 1922a, 51–52).

The spiritual transformation occurred once Siang’s gaze engaged with that of Saint Mary’s statue (Pelerzi 1922a, 52). As in other religious traditions, the exchange of gazes is considered one of the primary tools to experience the supernatural and maintain a channel with it (Babb 1981). The Virgin Mary’s sacred aura introduced a feeling of vividness, as the statue itself was moving and changing shape according to Siang’s feelings (Pelerzi 1922a, 52). Siang’s transfiguration is further described as a ray of light that was progressively enlightening her heart.

Siang’s conversion and the consequent conflicts with her father were sustained by the intersubjective bond she established with Lucia and her family. The latter were cultural tricksters, still sharing Siang’s culture but, at the same time, able to articulate the differences between the two religions, their materiality, and the allegedly moral superiority of Catholicism through their daily habits and conversations. The mutual process of “becoming”—the missionary becoming Chinese and the folk believer becoming Catholic—is continuously tested by the cultural sensitivity of fellow converts and local catechists. Luigi Calza, in a letter written on the 16th of January and published in the April issue of *Fede e Civiltà* (Calza 1907, 59), also defined Chinese catechists as key intermediaries who can reach folk believers when missionaries cannot because of cultural barriers.

Whilst Pelerzi was proactive in fabricating Catholic materiality, he indirectly influenced iconoclastic acts by new converts. In his “Il diavolo nel pozzo” (The devil in the well), contained in *Un missionario racconta*, or the short story “Michelino l’iconoclasta” (Michelino the iconoclastic), which appeared in *Le Missioni Illustrate* (Illustrated Missions),⁵ children who have followed his teachings are usually the perpetrators of intentional destruction of “idols” to punish pagan neighbors or defend themselves from the latter’s immoral presence (Pelerzi 1935a, 44–48; 1935b).

On the one hand, the missionary was complicit, secretly enjoying these childish pranks; on the other hand, he attempted to soften direct acts of iconoclasm, recommending prudence and gradualness in eradicating Chinese folk religion. These measures were taken both to prevent any conflict from escalating between Catholics and the rest of the village and to secure a more spiritually robust process of conversion for folk believers, established through peaceful dialogue with other converts and missionaries.

New converts, however, had mixed feelings toward their conversion. For instance, Cecilia, a convert who rescued a girl from being sacrificed in the “pagoda” to a god (*La consacrata*, The Consecrated, Pelerzi 1924b), was terrified that the spirits would

vindicate her behavior, then realizing, after praying in church, that she should not fear mere “pieces of wood.” The narrator commented that past religious education leaves “reminiscences” that must be treated throughout converts’ spiritual paths (cfr. Guareschi 1914, 86–91).

Although these descriptions of converts’ feelings are distorted by Pelerzi’s subjectivity and utopian missionary plans, they partially reflect the sense of fear and reverence toward gods in Chinese folk worship. Secondary sources on the spread of Christianity in China in different historical epochs (Hsia 2010; Kao 2020; Liu 2009) show how the transition to a new religious identity was mediated and supported by forms of knowledge, embodied practices, and emotional expressions (i.e., dreams) that converts had learnt from their previous lives as folk religious worshippers. Converts translated the Bible using vocabulary which referred to folk gods’ hierarchy and pilgrimage, whilst revering Catholic holy artifacts as lucky charms to remove disasters in folk religion. Examples of converts’ negotiations between folk religion and Catholicism can also be found in missionary accounts. As reported in Disma Guareschi (1915, 209), Catholic materiality was considered essential by new converts for filling the empty family altars, whose statues and tablets were burnt as proof of their willingness to convert to Catholicism. Folk believers could eventually accept Catholic statues and mistake them as Chinese folk religious variants (Pelerzi 1929, 20). Sacred water was also requested by converts as a means of purification of the former family altars and for protecting themselves from potential, vengeful spirits (Guareschi 1914, 87; 1916, 11). Instead of reading converts’ mixed feelings as a sign of their “spiritual weakness,” I interpret them as negotiations between their new faith and the impact that the spread of Catholicism had on their larger communities.

Religious artifacts and ritual practices were, for the Chinese and the missionaries, an ambiguous medium within their relationships. From a missionary perspective, Chinese folk deities’ statues were necessary for establishing a terrain of dialogue, providing tools for missionaries’ “becoming Chinese” and sustaining the gradual experiential and religious metamorphosis of folk believers into Catholics. Chinese folk religious statuary and other ritual implements should also be the target of iconoclasm and substituted with Jesus Christ, the Virgin Mary’s statuary, and a rosary. From a Chinese folk religious perspective, missionary iconoclasm could compromise the harmony between spiritual forces and society at large. Consequently, converts applied sensitivity to and knowledge of Chinese folk religion to regulate their new religious identity and prevent possible reactions of god spirits to it. If, in the eyes of missionaries such as Disma Guareschi, seeing new converts burning their domestic deities’ statues and ancestral tablets as an act of iconoclasm signaled a triumph of Catholicism, for converts it was a careful, although controversial, ritual of *tuishen* for releasing god spirits to heaven and, therefore, being released from the cultic responsibilities toward them.

6 | Returning to the Hollowed Buddha: Some Conclusions

I started this journey because I was unsatisfied with the scant and contradictory information about the hollowed Buddha I had

at my disposal. The museum entry the archivist copied for me only mentioned that Monsignor Luigi Calza, future archbishop, purchased it in 1912. The embodied uncanniness, resulting from the echo in the hollowed Buddha of my ethnographic experience, signaled the existence of information lurking beneath the statue. Oral narratives also did not accord with the museum entry: missionaries did not have the financial resources to buy Chinese artifacts. The presence of this Buddha might indicate more than a simple purchase of a religious item.

This work has articulated several traces of missionaries' encounters with folk believers and their deities' statues, enabling me to take the additional meaning of the hollowed Buddha seriously, which I sensed that July day. Several material traces unfolded: the Buddha statue itself with its sign of deconsecration; images and drawings illustrating deconsecrated Chinese folk deities' statues as circulating in *Fede e civiltà*; references to Chinese folk god statues being mutilated or left decaying, as well as feared by missionaries and local Chinese, both Catholic and "pagan." These literary traces are historiographically unconventional as they are mostly fictional elaborations of what we can presume were missionaries' experiences and relationships with folk believers in Henan. They cannot substitute for thorough provenance research. However, given the museum archives' inaccessibility, engaging with missionary writings enabled me to grasp the atmosphere in which the unsealing of the Buddha's hollow presumably took place.

The investigation of this hollowed Buddha resonated with provenance research in other museum collections of Chinese folk deities' statues and ethnographic fieldwork in Taiwan that I was conducting in parallel, thus adding further nuances to missionary literature. I realized that collecting hollowed Chinese folk deities' statues was a practice more rooted, widespread, and persistent throughout centuries than I could imagine. For instance, the Religionskundliche Sammlung of Philipps-University Marburg has hollowed Chinese folk god statues that were collected by Evangelical missionaries in the 1920s, as well as by German sinologists in the 1980s. The latter were purchased in an antique shop in Taipei and entered the museum already with their hollows unsealed. Unsealing the god statues' hollows in secondhand and art markets in Taiwan is an established practice, as confirmed to me by interlocutors, and it is done for various reasons that might go beyond mere protection from god and ghost spirits. The sacred matter that resided inside god statues can be reused for amulets or reinstalled in another statue. This is the case, for instance, of Taiwanese temples when they want to protect ancient statues from theft, thereby sculpting a new statue whilst displaying the ancient one in an exhibition space protected by alarms (Gamberi and Wang 2025).

The hollowed Buddha statue in Parma is, therefore, a polysemic trace which suggests that either missionaries or converts could have taken out its sacred interiors. The missionaries receiving the Buddha from Calza might have deconsecrated it to study it closely, as they lived at a time when museum practice was not yet influenced by ethical concerns (Reedy 1991). The fact that missionaries themselves had ambiguous emotions toward an artifact that was part of an "idolatric" religion might have reassured their eventual doubts on the legitimacy of unsealing the Buddha's hollow, as in the case of Silvestri. Recent converts

could have given the statue to Calza and, consequently, unsealed the statue's hollow as a protective measure to prevent any spiritual attacks by keeping the statue rather than burning it after *tuishen*. Calza could have paid converts for compensating their family members for the loss of the domestic altar and, therefore, mitigating any conflict. The Buddha's hollow could have already been unsealed if Calza had purchased it from an antique shop. The sacred substance could also have been transferred to another statue, used for amulets, or exchanged as precious material by folk believers as an act of resistance to missionaries or a continuation of a consolidated practice toward discarded sacred statues.

The arrival of the hollowed Buddha in Parma reinforced Xaverian "missionary strategy," along with many other hollowed Chinese folk deities' statues circulated within museum galleries, on printed postcards, or on public view during the Institute's "flea" market or missionary theatrical performances. Its hollowed back reflected the unequal relationships between folk believers and missionaries in Henan at that time. The Buddha, however, also accounted for converts' agency and the reinscription of conversions to Catholicism within the metamorphic transformation of gods' sacred power in Chinese folk religion. Folk believers' destructions of their god statues, rather than being a sign of the weakness of their "idolatric cult," reflected a different conceptualization of god spirits as highly metamorphic and mutable, taking possession of different statues, natural elements, or simply lingering in the environment but extremely powerful.

Expanding the concept of "trace" to unconventional and ahistorical elements, such as fiction and contemporary embodied experiences, sheds light on collections that are rarely examined by scholars and whose archives are inaccessible. The multiple stories that reverberate through the encounter of Xaverian missionaries with folk believers in Henan might or might not have taken place in the past. However, they are certainly useful for elaborating complex and layered interpretations of missionary material going beyond stereotypical views of converts as passive recipients of missionary preaching and missionaries either as "saviors" or as "amateurish" and, therefore, anthropologically illiterate (Kreps 2024).

Acknowledgments

I would like to express my gratitude to the staff of the Museum of Chinese Art and Ethnography, the Xaverian Institute's library and archives, as well as to the Xaverian missionaries I encountered in Taiwan along with their parish's worshippers. I also would like to thank the anonymous reviewers for their insightful comments. Without this composite group of people, this research could not reach an end. Open access publishing facilitated by Univerzita Palackeho v Olomouci, as part of the Wiley - CzechELib agreement.

Funding

This work is part of the postdoctoral project "Processual Decay Paradigm (PDP): Problematizing Museums and Asian Religions." PDP is supported by the Program Johannes Amos Comenius (OP JAC) of the Czech Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports within the Project "MSCA Fellowships at Palacký University II." CZ.02.01.01/00/22_010/0006945, run at Palacký University in Olomouc, Czech Republic.

Ethics Statement

This research was approved by the Research Ethics Board of the UPOL Faculty of Arts under Ref. No. 2/2024, issued on the 9th of May 2024.

Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings will be available in Zenodo by the end of Valentina Gamberi's fellowship (end of February).

Endnotes

¹ Buddha statues are found in certain temples that combine Buddhist and folk religious rituals. *Tuishen*, although having different ritual procedures and nuances from folk religion, is also part of Buddhism. Since Xaverian missionaries did not distinguish between Daoism and Buddhism—for instance, using the term “pagoda” to refer to any temple in Henan—and the iconographic material that informed this research mainly showed folk god statues, this study will primarily focus on folk religion rather than Buddhism. Han folk religion is usually referred to in English as “Chinese folk religion” or “folk religion,” regardless of the provenance of the rituals across the Chinese communities in Asia. For a smoother reading, I often use the terms “Chinese folk god statues” or “Chinese folk deities’ statues.”

² Although Henan folk religion differs from that practiced in Taiwan, due to the development of distinct local cults, I decided to compare what I was reading in missionary sources with my fieldwork experience, focusing on common practices and rituals observed across Chinese folk religion in Asian regions.

³ I conducted formal and informal interviews, maintaining the anonymity of my interlocutors. The methodology adopted was assessed by the Ethical Review Board of my faculty.

⁴ The Archangel Michael defeated Lucifer and the other rebel angels by piercing them with his sword. In the missionaries' view, therefore, a pierced religious statue is a tangible sign of the devil.

⁵ This was the name of *Fede e Civiltà* from 1927 to 1947.

References

Primary Sources

Bonardi, G. 1904. “Una scorsa in città e una visita alla pagoda di Nan-Yan-Fu.” *Fede e Civiltà* I, no. 8: 122–123.

1921. *Nel campo delle missioni*. Institute for Foreign Missions.

Calza, L. 1907. “Siang Shien, 16 gennaio 1907—Dai nostri.” *Fede e Civiltà* IV, no. 4: 57–59.

Guareschi, D. 1914. “Storia di una conversione.” *Fede e Civiltà* XI, no. 5: 86–91.

1915. “I nostri dei non li vogliamo più.” *Fede e Civiltà* XII, no. 11: 204–209.

1916. “Cenni d'una recente conversione.” *Fede e Civiltà* XIII, no. 1: 8–11.

Pelerzi, E. 1919. “Giuseppe Siao. Confessore della fede per il M. P. Eugenio Pelerzi, Missionario Apostolico.” *Fede e Civiltà* XVI, no. 2: 58–59.

1920. “Inter Gentes—Terzo viaggio 1920.” *Fede e Civiltà* XVII, no. 8: 146–153.

1921. *Giuseppe Siao. Confessore della fede in Cina*. Institute of Foreign Missions.

1922a. *La figlia del mandarino*. Institute of Foreign Missions.

1922b. *Tipi e scorci di vita cinese*. Institute of Foreign Missions.

1922c. “Le vicende di una pagoda.” *Fede e Civiltà* XIX, no. 13: 92–94.

1924a. “La vita dei cinesi.” *Fede e Civiltà* XXI, no. 3: 55–58.

1924b. *La consacrata*. Institute of Foreign Missions.

1929. *La derelitta di Go-Ce*. Institute of Foreign Missions.

1935a. *Un missionario racconta*. Institute of Foreign Missions.

1935b. “Michelino l'iconoclasta.” *Le Missioni Illustrate* XXXIII, no. 4: 121–125.

Può-Mate. 1913. “La Sala dei Martiri.” *Fede e Civiltà* X, no. 1: 1–6.

Silvestri, E. 1915a. “A che servono i buchi che gli idoli hanno dietro la schiena?” *Fede e Civiltà* XII, no. 3: 50–54.

1915b. “In una pagoda cinese.” *Fede e Civiltà* XII, no. 9: 169–172.

Toscano, G. M. 1965. *Museo d'arte cinese di Parma*. Istituto Saveriano Missioni Estere.

Secondary Source

Amaral, A. R. 2020. “Exhibiting Faith Against an Imperial Background.” *Journal of Religion in Africa* 50, no. 1/2: 79–108.

Babb, L. A. 1981. “Glancing: Visual Interaction in Hinduism.” *Journal of Anthropological Research* 37, no. 4: 387–401.

Beekers, D. 2016. “Sacred Residue, in the Urban Sacred: How Religion Makes and Takes Place.” In *Amsterdam, Berlin and London/Städtisch-religiöse Arrangements in Amsterdam, Berlin und London*, edited by S. Lanwerd, 39–41. Metropol.

Bodenstein, F., M. von Oswald, D. Otoiu, and A. Seiderer, eds. 2024. *Traces du dé/colonial au musée*. Horizons d'Attente.

Brevaglieri, S. 2022. “Missionary Collecting Between Object Eradications and Re-Sedimentations. An Introduction.” *Quaderni Storici* 1: 4–17.

Corbey, R., and F. K. Weener. 2015. “Collecting While Converting: Missionaries and Ethnographics.” *Journal of Art Historiography* 12: 1–14.

Corin, E. 2020. “The Power of Traces.” *Ethos* 47, no. 4: 440–450.

Ferro, E. 2014. “Mons. Conforti vive, quasi in ombra, il suo 25° di Sacerdozio.” *Parma Negli Anni: Società Civile e Religiosa* 18: 63–108.

2019. *Sui luoghi di Guido Maria Conforti*. Centro Studi Confortiani Saveriani.

Gamberi, V., and S. Wang. 2025. “Religion on Display: A Comparative Study of the Museum of World Religions and Exhibition Spaces in Temples in Taiwan.” In *The Museum in Asia*, edited by Y. Cai, 37–48. Routledge.

Gasparotto, I. 2018. “Costruire l'alterità. Le collezioni etnografiche dei missionari cattolici italiani (1850–1925): genealogie ed allestimenti museali.” PhD Dissertation, University of Padua.

Ginzburg, C. 2013. *Clues, Myths, and the Historical Method*. John Hopkins University Press.

Harrison, H. 2013. *The Missionary's Curse and Other Tales From a Chinese Catholic Village*. University of California Press.

Hasinoff, E. L. 2010. “The Missionary Exhibit.” *Museum History Journal* 3, no. 1: 81–102. <https://doi.org/10.1179/mhj.2010.3.1.81>.

2011. *Faith in Objects. American Missionary Exposition in the Early Twentieth Century*. Palgrave Macmillan.

Hsia, R. P.-C. 2010. “Dreams and Conversions: A Comparative Analysis of Catholic and Buddhist Dreams in Ming and Qing China. Part Two.” *Journal of Religious History* 34, no. 2: 111–141.

- Iurman, E. 2016. *Cose di Cina quotidiana (1900–1950)*. Museum of Chinese Art and Ethnographic Editions.
- Jenz, F., and H. Acke. 2013. "Introduction." In *Missions and Media. The Politics of Missionary Periodicals in the Long Nineteenth Century*, 9–15. Franz Steiner Verlag.
- Kao, C.-Y. 2020. "Materiality in the Absence of the Church: Practising Protestantism During China's Cultural Revolution." *History and Anthropology* 31, no. 5: 563–582. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02757206.2020.1805738>.
- Kreps, C. 2024. "Missionaries, Anthropologists, Museums. Instrumentalism and Lessons for Progressive Museology." In *Pragmatic Imagination and the New Museum Anthropology*, edited by J. C. Hodge and C. Kreps, 184–205. Routledge.
- Liu, L.-M. 2009. "Catholic Faith in the Perspective of Chinese Rural Culture: Focusing on Catholicism in North China During the Late Qing Dynasty." [In Simplified Mandarin.] *Journal of Jinan University, Social Sciences Edition* 19, no. 1: 50–55.
- Loder-Neuhold, R. 2019. "Crocodiles, Masks and Madonnas. Catholic Mission Museums in German-Speaking Europe." PhD diss., Uppsala University.
- Marsh, D. 2016. "Trace Ethnography, Affect and Institutional Ecologies in the Distributed Records of a Plaster Model." *Museum Anthropology* 39, no. 2: 111–129.
- Meyer, B. 2024. "'Idols' in the Museum: Legacies of Missionary Iconoclasm." In *Image Controversies: Contemporary Iconoclasm in Art, Media and Cultural Heritage*, edited by B. Mersmann, C. Kruse, and A. Bartetzky, 108–130. De Gruyter.
- Mitter, P. 1992. *Much Maligned Monsters. A History of European Reactions to Indian Art*. University of Chicago Press.
- Mooren, J., K. Stutje, and F. van Kree. 2022. "Clues. Research Into Provenance History and Significance of Cultural Objects and Collections Acquired in Colonial Situations. Final Report." NIOD, Stichting National Museum Van Wereldculturen and Rijks Museum. <https://www.niod.nl/en/publications/clues-PPROCE>.
- Napolitano, V. 2015. "Anthropology and Traces." *Anthropological Theory* 15, no. 1: 47–67. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1463499614554239>.
- Palmié, S., and C. Stewart. 2016. "Introduction: For an Anthropology of History." *HAU: Journal of Ethnographic Theory* 6, no. 1: 207–236.
- Palmié, S., and C. Stewart. 2019. "Introduction: The Varieties of Historical Experience." In *The Varieties of Historical Experience*, 1–30. Routledge.
- Reedy, C. L. 1991. "The Opening of Consecrated Tibetan Bronzes With Interior Contents: Scholarly, Conservation, and Ethical Considerations." *Journal of the American Institute for Conservation* 30, no. 1: 13–34.
- Reich, A. K. 2024. "Conceptions of Divinity: Statue Making in Contemporary Taiwan and the Ritual of Embedding the Spirit (Rushen)." *Material Religion* 20, no. 3–4: 205–232.
- Scholz, M. A. 2025. "Ethnographic Objects and Provenance From Missionary Contexts. The Chile Missions and the Bavarian Capuchins and Their Museum in Altötting, 1896-1932." In *Crosscultural Heritage. Critical Approaches to Missionary Legacies*, edited by J. Van Mulder, T. Coomans, and D. Vansacker, 137–159. Leuven University Press.
- Smith, C. 2018. "Accumulating History: Dirt, Remains and Urban Decay in Nairobi." *Social Dynamics* 44, no. 1: 107–127.
- Stoler, A. L. 2013. *Imperial Debris*. Duke University Press.
- Verband der Museen der Schweiz. 2022. "Provenienzforschung im Museum II: Sammlungen aus kolonialen Kontexten. Grundlagen und Einführung in die Praxis." <https://www.museums.ch/de/fachwelt/angebote/publikationen/provenienzforschung-koloniale-sammlungen-952.html>.
- Wingfield, C. 2017. "Missionary Museums." In *Religion in Museums: Global and Multidisciplinary Perspectives*, edited by G. Buggeln, C. Paine, and B. S. Plate, 231–239. Bloomsbury.
- Wu, A. M. 2016. *From Christ to Confucius. German Missionaries, Chinese Christians, and the Globalization of Christianity, 1860–1950*. Yale University Press.